

The Event Horizon Telescope Science Gateway - Progress and Lessons Learned

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Abstract—The Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) recently used 10 petabyte-scale observation data to construct the first images of black holes and 100 terabyte-scale simulation data to constrain the plasma properties around supermassive black holes. This work leveraged the Open Science Grid (OSG) high throughput resources provided by the Partnership to Advance Throughput Computing (PATH). While EHT has successfully utilized PATH to create the most extensive black hole simulation library to date, the broad adoption of this resource for data processing has been slower. The sophisticated command-line-driven HTCondor environment creates barriers for less technical researchers, limiting PATH’s reach and impact on the broader astronomy and science communities. The Cyberinfrastructure Integration Research Center (CIRC) at Indiana University was awarded an NSF EAGER award to collaborate with EHT and PATH to implement a targeted science gateway instance that integrates critical EHT workflows to leverage OSG within the Apache Airavata framework. This work began in July of 2023. The EHT Science Gateway project was introduced to the Gateways community at last year’s Gateways 2023 event. This paper and presentation will detail the work during the project’s design, development, implementation, and release phases. The production release is scheduled for July 2024.

Index Terms—High Throughput Computing, User Experience, Gateways for Science, Astrophysics, Apache Airavata

I. INTRODUCTION

The Partnership to Advance Throughput Computing (PATH) is the NSF’s premier resource for high throughput computing (HTC), delivering over 139 million core hours last year (one-year period ending 25-May 2024) to multi-institutional projects and an additional 274 million core hours to smaller groups that constitute the Open Science Grid (OSG) Connect community [1]. Usage groups include some of the most high-profile research investments by the NSF, such as the multi-institutional Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) collaboration. EHT used 10 petabyte-scale observation data to construct the first images of black holes and 100 terabyte-scale simulation data to constrain the plasma properties around supermassive black holes. While the EHT has successfully utilized PATH to create the biggest black hole simulation library to date, the broad adoption of this resource is much slower for data

processing. The sophisticated OSG command-line-driven environment turns out to be a major barrier to the less technical users, limiting PATH’s reach and impact within the wider astronomy and science communities.

Science gateways [2] have proven a successful mechanism for broadening access to scientific cyberinfrastructure (CI) by providing science-centric user environments tailored to end-user communities. An emerging and potentially transformative area of research in science gateway development involves the integration of established science gateway technologies with the methodologies of human-computer interactions (HCI) and user experience-based (UX) design.

To overcome barriers to adoption and create a highly functional science gateway environment that can effectively utilize the computing power of HTC resources, this project, which began in July 2023, will focus on the EHT community’s use of PATH as a case study for this methodological approach. This exploratory project aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of combining human-computer interaction design methodologies with science gateway technologies, thereby enhancing the EHT’s analysis of large astronomical data sets. This novel approach has the potential to transform both astrophysics and high throughput computing, offering a fresh perspective that benefits existing PATH user communities and supports the growth of PATH to include new research teams and projects.

Our team consists of experienced leaders from the EHT, HTC, and science gateways communities, bringing together a wealth of expertise in coupling CI resources with science stakeholder workflows and possessing in-depth knowledge of the EHT ecosystem. Working alongside these leaders are a science gateway developer and a graduate student from the Human-Centered Computing Department at Indiana University as well as a postdoctoral researcher in astronomy from the University of Arizona. Together, we have designed, prototyped, tested, and will release the EHT science gateway in July of 2024. The resulting science gateway will be highly functional and designed to meet the HTC needs for researchers ranging from experienced researchers to students. By prioritizing UX design and emphasizing the necessary human-computer interactions within a science gateway environment, we have

ensured a positive experience for EHT researchers, fostering continued engagement and reliance on PATH HTC resources.

While this project is short-term and focuses on the EHT collaboration, the foundational work of integrating science gateways with PATH-provided resources has the potential for long-term benefits for both the science gateway and PATH communities. Science gateways will enhance their toolbox of offerings by incorporating high-capacity, high-availability resources. PATH will get a UX-centric access method, providing an entry point for users unfamiliar with command-line interfaces and with minimal time or effort available to learn new technologies on their path to discovery.

II. EHT SCIENCE GATEWAY PROTOTYPE

In 2022, CIRC collaborated with EHT researchers from the University of Arizona to develop a proof of concept for the EHT gateway [3] as part of the XSEDE Extended Collaborative Support Services program. The proof of concept version demonstrated the basic integration of PATH resources with Apache Airavata, but it lacked the advanced functionality required by a large number of EHT researchers and did not incorporate user requirements or UX design methods. The current project builds on the proof of concept by creating a highly functional science gateway. This gateway will cater to a large portion of the EHT community and accommodate various levels of analysis tasks.

III. PROJECT OBJECTIVES

This project is divided into three overarching objectives.

- 1) Deliver a highly functional, UX-centric gateway to the EHT project. This gateway will enable the integration of existing workflows that leverage OSPool resources.
- 2) Address the technical hurdles to allow the utilization of HTC resources from a science gateway environment within the Apache Airavata framework.
- 3) Conduct targeted outreach efforts aimed at astronomy researchers and the CI community to amplify the impact of the project.

IV. THE EVENT HORIZON TELESCOPE GATEWAY

The prototype EHT gateway described previously allowed single runs of the ipole application on PATH resources and was demonstrated in a collaboration-wide training webinar. The proposed work will extend this prototype to launch large-scale image analysis from science gateways on PATH. We have focused on the most widely used EHT application, ipole, which provides spacial and numerical analysis of black hole images from the eight ground-based radio telescopes which make up the EHT international collaboration.

V. USER EXPERIENCE DESIGN (UXD)

Our approach to designing the platform for EHT scientists using OSG resources has followed the double-diamond framework [4], which comprises four stages: Discover, Define, Develop, and Deliver. Here's a detailed overview of our process at each stage and our current status:

Fig. 1. Black hole simulation library generated for interpreting the image of the supermassive black hole at the center of the Milky Way. The computation was done on PATH-provided resources.

(1) Discover: In the Discover phase, we focused on understanding user needs. We immersed ourselves in the world of EHT scientists by engaging in conversations with stakeholders and analyzing user workflows. This exploration allowed us to identify pain points, user preferences, and specific challenges scientists face when using the OSG platform. By tracing the journey from job submission to the receipt of output files, we uncovered a crucial need for interactive analysis of output files and the pivotal role of post-processing in their research.

(2) Define: During the Define phase, we synthesized our findings from the Discover phase to pinpoint the core issues and user requirements. We revisited a previous proof of concept and conducted heuristic analyses to validate our initial insights. This helped us identify what worked well and areas needing improvement. By closely collaborating with two expert OSG users, we refined our understanding of user requirements. These interactions revealed the necessity for significant platform revisions, such as restructuring the platform to support multiple job submissions and improving information presentation for better clarity and ease of navigation.

(3) Develop: In the Develop phase, we transitioned from insights to solutions. Based on our research findings, we created three personas representing the diverse user types within the EHT community:

- 1) Expert Users with High Coding Skills: These users need a platform offering customization options and advanced scripting capabilities.
- 2) Novice Users, Early Researchers with Limited Coding Skills: These users seek user-friendly interfaces and intuitive workflows to simplify the submission process.
- 3) Students: This group includes users who utilize the platform for educational purposes.

We used these personas to guide our design decisions, ensuring the platform meets the unique needs of each user type. Additionally, we explored various use cases to anticipate a wide range of user interactions, enhancing the platform's adaptability and responsiveness. We mapped out the user journey from the homepage to job submission completion, detailing each step to ensure a seamless user experience.

(4) Deliver: We are currently in the Deliver phase, where we implement and refine our solutions based on iterative testing and feedback. Users begin their journey at the homepage, where they can sign up or log in. Upon logging in, they are directed to a personalized dashboard providing an overview of active applications, job statuses, and recent submissions. Users then select their desired application and choose their preferred submission method, whether through a web form for novices or a Python script for experts. Post-submission, users can monitor job progress and access completed analyses directly from the dashboard.

To sum up, throughout the design process, we identified several key takeaways that have significantly informed our development approach and feature prioritization. One of the highest priorities for the UI was to submit jobs to the OSG as intuitively as possible. We recognized that many users lacked the technical expertise to navigate complex command-line interfaces, so streamlining this process became critical. In this regard, we used several techniques such as information icons and tooltips to provide users with on-demand guidance throughout the submission process. Information icons next to key fields offered detailed explanations of what was required without overwhelming users with technical jargon. Furthermore, we organized the job submission process into a clear, step-by-step sequence, ensuring that users were guided through each necessary action, reducing the risk of error or incomplete submissions. Additionally, the platform provides real-time validation and feedback if a submission field is incomplete or contains incorrect data, enabling users to correct mistakes before submission.

While the majority of the features were made available through the user-friendly UI, the outcome analysis was specifically left for Jupyter notebooks. This decision was made because Jupyter offers more flexibility for advanced users to perform detailed and customizable analysis. However, to accommodate users with less experience in Jupyter, we provide pre-prepared workbook templates that guide them through the analysis process. These templates reduce the need for in-depth knowledge of Jupyter while still offering powerful analytical capabilities.

By adhering to the double-diamond framework, we have systematically developed a user-centered platform that addresses the specific needs and challenges of EHT scientists, ensuring a robust and responsive user experience.

VI. INTEGRATION WITH APACHE AIRAVATA

Our project is implementing a web-based science gateway that leverages the open-source Apache Airavata [5] gateway framework. The Airavata Django Portal is a web interface to the Apache Airavata API implemented using the Python Django web framework. The Airavata Django Portal can be used as is for a full-featured web-based science gateway. It can also be customized through various plugins to add domain-specific functionality. The primary objective of EHT gateway is to provide users with a streamlined and user-friendly interface for interacting with PATH resources, eliminating the

challenges associated with command-line interfaces for users familiar with browser-based interfaces.

By implementing an Apache Airavata-based gateway with a graphical user interface (GUI), we will significantly reduce the learning curve associated with command-line interfaces, enabling more researchers to utilize HTC resources effectively. The web interface will be designed to be user friendly, providing clear instructions and visual aids to guide users through the process. This will make the system more accessible to researchers with varying levels of technical proficiency. Web-based interfaces provided by Apache Airavata have proved highly effective, allowing researchers to more quickly and efficiently utilize high performance computing (HPC) environments than traditional command-line interfaces. Moreover, the OSPool—accessible through Apache Airavata middleware—provides hundreds of thousands of hours of daily access to HTC resources, further enhancing its appeal to the scientific community.

Fig. 2. A depiction of the proposed EHT science gateway, which will enable users to interact with Apache Airavata’s gateway services and access the OSPool through HTCCondor access points.

While coupling the Apache Airavata science gateway framework with PATH resources is an undoubtedly significant advancement and beneficial to both the HTC and Apache Airavata communities, it has taken substantial effort to fully integrate the two systems beyond a mere proof of concept. Our project will provide a highly integrated EHT portal while recording and addressing the challenges of interactions between web-based environments and HTC workload creation and submission. By addressing these challenges, we seek to streamline the adoption process for future projects that leverage these technologies. This, in turn, will enable the seamless utilization of HTC resources within science gateway environments.

In April of 2024, the first large-scale test run was submitted from the EHT gateway for OSG analysis. This test consisted of 3000 telescope images and considered six unique parameter conditions for 36000 HTC jobs. This run was completed in less than 24 hours. While some errors were encountered, more than 94% were completed successfully. By re-compiling iPole application with less aggressive optimization flags and increasing the value max_retries in submission, the error rates have reduced to less than 0.04% in the latest experiments.

The project has drawn upon the insights gained from PATH’s EHT integration and concurrent survey work. This collaborative effort has established a strong foundation for supporting

additional research communities. The PATH project leadership, the science gateways community, and the project management are jointly identifying these communities.

VII. TRAINING AND OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

The PATH team and the CIRC team at IU conducted joint tutorials throughout the 2022 calendar year. This included delivering an EHT-targeted webinar in September and conducting a tutorial at the Gateways 2022 conference. Building upon these events, we will further refine the materials and continue to provide training at CI events and target existing projects that could benefit from the collaborative PATH and CIRC relationship.

To expand our outreach efforts, upon production release of the EHT Science Gateway, the project team will specifically target EHT user groups at semiannual, in-person EHT collaboration meetings as well as through an online tutorial webinar event that we will organize. These outreach events feature tutorials focused on increasing the user base and identifying user needs for future functionality. In 2024, we plan to submit papers to the PEARC and the Science Gateways conference. We also hope to initiate engagements with two additional PATH-recommended communities currently using HTC resources but are likely to embrace science gateways during High Throughput Week in July 2024.

By strategically targeting these events and communities, we aim to enhance user engagement, expand the user base, and identify opportunities for collaboration and future development within the PATH framework.

A. Collaboration

The project receives dedicated effort and oversight from the funded institutions of Indiana University and the University of Arizona. The University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, MIT Haystack Observatory, the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics, and the Harvard Black Hole Initiative will provide additional community technical and research support. To further strengthen the project, we will leverage the support and operational assistance of the PATH team from the University of Wisconsin–Madison and Morgridge Institute for Research. This collaboration entails hosting an OSPool Access Point and providing support for HTCondor integration issues that may arise throughout the project’s duration.

Before the formal development process of the platform, informal consultations with some of these key stakeholders and potential collaborators were an integral part of the planning phase. These early conversations helped highlight some of the challenges and best practices learned from similar projects. As the project evolves, we plan to formalize this feedback loop with surveys and interviews to better capture insights and avoid pitfalls experienced by others in the astronomy community. By incorporating feedback from both internal users and external collaborators, we aim to ensure the gateway remains responsive to evolving user needs and adaptable to broader astronomical applications.

VIII. PROJECT DELIVERABLES

The project receives dedicated effort and oversight from the funded institutions of Indiana University and the University of Arizona. The University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, MIT Haystack Observatory, the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics, and the Harvard Black Hole Initiative will provide additional community technical and research support. To further strengthen the project, we will leverage the support and operational assistance of the PATH team from the University of Wisconsin–Madison and Morgridge Institute for Research. This collaboration entails hosting an OSPool Access Point and providing support for HTCondor integration issues that may arise throughout the project.

IX. COLLABORATION

The principal project deliverable is a fully functional EHT Science Gateway. This gateway will support the EHT needs for preparing and submitting black hole image simulation (ipole) to PATH resources. A significant amount of effort has been concentrated on user experience (UX) design, allowing these applications to be widely usable by EHT scientists through science gateway user interfaces. We will integrate the lessons learned from the UX-based design and development of the EHT science gateway to integrate new science gateway portals that leverage HTC resources. These may include additional astronomy communities (such as the Vera Rubin Observatory), and other current OSPool users identified by our PATH collaborators. We will submit this work at both cyberinfrastructure-focused conferences (PEARC, High Throughput Week, Gateways) and to the multi-messenger astronomy community (Semi-annual EHT Collaboration Meetings). These outreach deliverables will include developer and user tutorials and training events.

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